

**VARIETY OF ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS OF PRECOCIOUS PUBERTY IN BOYS:
PRESENTATION OF THREE CLINICAL CASES**

¹Uralova D.U., ²Khalimova Z.Y., ³Abdullayeva A.U., ⁴Xolova D.Sh., ⁵Rahimova G.N.,
⁶Suleymanova F.N., ⁷Mehmanova S.U.

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7}Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology named after academician Y.Kh.Turakulov, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8357803>

Abstract. Precocious puberty is a specific pediatric disease characterized by the appearance of secondary sexual characteristics before 8 years in girls and 9 years in boys. It is divided into two categories: central precocious puberty, characterized by the premature activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis, and peripheral precocious puberty presents when premature sexual development is dependent on steroid production regardless of gonadotropin secretion. In the case of boys precocious puberty is more often associated with identifiable organic disorders of the central nervous system, adrenal glands or testes. The purpose of this article was to discuss etiopathogenesis of precocious puberty in boys in three cases and to provide the approach to its diagnosis, differentiation and treatment.

Keywords: precocious puberty, central precocious puberty, peripheral precocious puberty, congenital adrenal hyperplasia, hamartoma, adrenocortical carcinoma, growth zones, bone age, hypopituitarism, external genitalia.

Аннотация. Преждевременное половое развитие – специфическое педиатрическое заболевание, характеризующееся появлением вторичных половых признаков до 8 лет у девочек и 9 лет у мальчиков. Различают две формы ППР: центральный ППР, характеризующееся преждевременной активацией гипоталамо-гипофизарно-гонадной оси, и периферическое ППР, которое проявляется, когда появления вторичных половых признаков зависит от продукции стероидов независимо от секреции гонадотропинов. У мальчиков преждевременное половое созревание чаще связано с выявленными органическими нарушениями центральной нервной системы, надпочечников или яичек. Цель данной статьи является обсудить этиопатогенез преждевременного полового созревания у мальчиков в трех клинических случаях и предложить подходы к его диагностике, дифференциации и лечению.

Ключевые слова: преждевременное половое развитие, центральное преждевременное половое развитие, периферическое преждевременное половое развитие, врожденная дисфункция коры надпочечников, гамартома, адренокортикальная карцинома, зоны роста, костный возраст, гипопитуитаризм, наружные гениталии.

Annotatsiya. Vaqtdan ilgari jinsiy yetilish – bu qizlarda 8 yoshgacha va o'g'il bolalarda yoshgacha ikkilamchi jinsiy belgilar paydo bo'lishi bilan tavsiflanadigan bolalar endokrin kasalligi hisoblanadi. Vaqtdan ilgari jinsiy yetilishning ikki turi farqlanadi: gipotalamus-gipofiz-gonadal o'qning erta faollashishi bilan tavsiflangan markaziy erta jinsiy rivojlanish va gonadotropinlar sekretsiyasiga bog'liq bo'lmagan steroidlar sekretsiyasiga bog'liq erta jinsiy rivojlanish. O'g'il bolalarda vaqtdan ilgari jinsiy yetilish ko'pincha markaziy nerv tizimi, buyrak usti bezlari yoki moyaklardagi o'smalar bilan bog'liq. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi o'g'il bolalarda vaqtdan ilgari balog'atga yetilishning etiopatogenezi, diagnostikasi, differensial diagnostikasi va davoga yondashuvlarni uchta klinik holat misolida muhokama qilishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: erta jinsiy yetilish, markaziy erta jinsiy yetilish, periferik erta jinsiy yetilish, buyrak usti bezi tug'ma giperplaziyasi, gamartoma, adrenokortika kartsinoma, o'sish zonalari, suyak yoshi, gipopituitarizm, tashqi jinsiy a'zolar.

Introduction

Precocious puberty (PP) has been defined by the development of secondary sexual characteristics before the age of 9 years in boys and 8 years in girls [Brito VN et al., 2008]. Historical data from Europe show a sharp decline in mean age at menarche from approximately 17 years in the early nineteenth century to approximately 13 years by the mid-twentieth century, with a minor decrement during the past 25–30 years [Sorensen K et al., 2012]. It is generally estimated to affect 1 in 5000–10,000 children; however, multiple countries throughout the world have described the increasing incidence and/or prevalence including the United States, Spain, France, Denmark, Korea, and China since the 1990s [Kim YJ et al., 2019]. Precocious puberty classified to gonadotropin-dependent (central, true), gonadotropin-independent (peripheral) and partial forms [V.A.Petryakova et al. 2021].

Case 1

A 5-year-old boy came to the consulting polyclinic of Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology named after academician Y.Kh.Turakulov (RSSPMCE). From the anamnesis, he was born with a weight of 3800 grams, and height of 54 centimeters, with normal appearance of external genitalia. His mother had early mild toxicosis and several colds during pregnancy. Parents are not related to each other. The disease began with the appearance of the signs of precocious puberty: enlargement of the external genitalia and the appearance of hair growth in the pubic area when he was 1-year-old.

At that time, they applied to the RSSPMCE; he was Tanner stage 3 for pubic hair development, length of the penis was 5 cm, volume of the testicles was 5 ml. The amounts of LH, FSH, testosterone, 17-oxyprogesterone, DHEA-S were measured in the blood. Abdominal ultrasound and computed tomography did not reveal tumors in the adrenal glands. The virile form of congenital adrenal hyperplasia (CAH) was diagnosed according to the level of the 17-oxyprogesterone (183 nmol/l). In addition to the level of the 17-OP, a mutation in the P453S exon of the CYP21 gene was detected in the genetic examination. The level of all other hormones was found to be at prepubertal level. Currently, hydrocortisone 10 mg (Cortef) is taken 1/3 tablet 3 times a day. During the examination, he was found to be 136 centimeters tall (above the 97th percentile) and 32 (above the 97th percentile) kilo in weight. X-ray of the left hand showed open growth zones, bone age of 13,5-14 years. The amount of hormones in the blood was as follows: 17-oxyprogesterone - 3,82 nmol/l; testosterone - 0,13 nmol/l; DHEA-S -120,2 mkg/dl; cortisole - 59,68 mkg/dl; LH - 1,07 mIU/ml; FSH - 0,34 mIU/ml; TSH - 2,7 mIU/l. Hydrocortisone dose of 1/2 tablet 3 times (15 mg/day) was prescribed to stop the development of secondary sexual characteristics and early bone age, and an examination was scheduled after 3 months for dynamic monitoring.

Case 2

A 3-year-old boy presented after a penis enlargement, pubic hair growth, hoarse voice, and enlarged testicles. These complaints started at age 2, and progressed rapidly. From anamnesis, parents are not related, siblings have no such signs. During the examination, he was Tanner stage 3 for axillary and pubic hair. The length of the penis was 6 cm, the volume of the testicles was 5

ml. Serum total testosterone was very high 22,4 nmol/l (normal for age 0,07-1,04 nmol/l); DHEA-S and cortisol were elevated at 25,2 nmol/l (normal for age 0,47-19,4 nmol/l) and at 35,4 mkg/dl (6,2-19,4 mkg/dl) respectively. Electrolytes, aldosterone and renin were normal.

Initial abdominal ultrasound and computed tomography revealed a heterogeneous mass in the left adrenal gland 5,5*4,6*7,1 cm. No pathological foci were detected in the CT scan of the chest and small pelvis. A left-sided adrenalectomy was performed at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Oncology. According to pathohistological conclusion, the tumor tissue was found to be adrenocortical carcinoma. He received carboplatin and daily oral mitotane. After 2 chemotherapy cycles, repeat PET-CT scan was found no pathological nodules.

X-ray of the left hand showed open growth zones, bone age of 10-11 years. Serum levels of testosterone, DHEA-S and cortisol were normalized within 6 month after surgery and 2 cycles of chemotherapy. Presently, serum levels of hormones were followings: LH – 1,01 mIU/ml (normal for age 0,04-3,6 mIU/ml), FSH – 0,18 mIU/ml (normal for age 0,3-4,6 mIU/ml), testosterone 0,08 nmol/l (normal for age 0,07-1,04 nmol/l), DHEA-S 27,7 mkg/dl (0,47-19,4 mkg/dl), 17 – OP – 0,09 ng/ml (normal for age 0,03-2,85 ng/ml), cortisol – 5,39 mkg/dl (6,2-19,4 mkg/dl). The patient was advised to undergo dynamic follow-up at the pediatric endocrinologist and oncologist every 6 month. He remains well at age 7 with no recurrence, secondary malignancy, or new malignancy.

Case 3

A 10-year-old boy presented with the complains of a hoarse voice, an enlarged penis, rapid growth, and rashes on his face. According to his mother, since he was 2 years old, his height growth accelerated, the penis has been lengthened and hairs have appeared on pubic area. He was born with a weight of 3500 grams, and height of 53 centimeters, with normal appearance of external genitalia. They did not consult a doctor until the age of 3. At the age of three, he was seen at the endocrinology center, and on brain MRI the heterogeneous mass was detected in the retrochiasmal area (12,4*15,7*11 mm). During the examination, he was Tanner stage 2 for pubic hair. The length of the penis was 5 cm, the volume of the testicles was 6 ml. β – Human Chorionic Gonadotropin in blood and cerebrospinal fluid, GH (Growth Hormone), IGF-1 (Insulin like Growth Factor-1), TSH, free-T4, 17-oxyprogesterone, DHEA - S were found to be normal for age, serum LH was 1,5 nmol/l, FSH was 2,4 nmol/l. Gonadotropin releasing hormone stimulation test with 100 mcg with GnRH analog, after one hour the LH level was found to be 8,4 IU/l. based on the results of the examinations, a diagnosis of hypothalamic hamartoma was made. Triptorelin acetate 3,75 mg was prescribed. Due to the high price, they only received it for 2 month.

At the moment, he was Tanner stage 3 for axillary and pubic hair development. The length of the penis was 8 cm, the volume of the testicles is 7 ml. The height is 141 cm (75 percentile), the weight 43 kg (above the 97th percentile). X-ray of the left hand revealed closed growth zones, bone age of 16 years. Hormonal tests showed the following: LH - 1,2 IU/l (normal for age 0,04-3,6 IU/l), FSH - 0,78 IU/l (normal for age 0,3-4,6 IU/l), 17-oxyprogesterone – 3,2 nmol/l (normal for age 1,9-6,52 nmol/l), testosterone 5,9 nmol/l (0,07-1,04 nmol/l), prolactin – 6,7 ng/ml (1,3-11,5 IU/l), growth hormone 1,3 mIU/l (normal for age 2,1 \pm 0,53 mIU/l). Brain MRI showed 12,7*15,5*10,2 mm sized mass in the retrochiasmal area. Operative treatment was not indicated due to the absence of neurological signs, hypopituitarism, and signs of diabetes insipidus, chiasmal syndrome and lack of hamartoma enlargement. Triptorelin acetate was prescribed for one year to stop sexual development. Follow-up every 6 month was defined.

Discussion

In our case series, boys were presented with signs of precocious puberty. The first two patients had peripheral and the third patient had central PP. Although precocious puberty occurs more frequently in girls, in the case of boys it is more often associated with identifiable organic disorders of the central nervous system, adrenal glands or testes [Krysiak R et al., 2014]. Adrenocortical tumors comprise 0.2% of pediatric cancers, with an incidence of 0.7 to 2.0 cases per million in the general population [Berstein L et al., 2020]. According to number of studies, the prevalence of organic cause of CPP in boys has been reported to range between 73 and 94% [Desai M et al., 1993]. According to our recent data, the most common etiology of precocious puberty in Uzbek boys were neurogenic CPP (25%) and CAH (37.5%).

One of the causes of peripheral PP is CAH, an autosomal recessive disease, characterized by an alteration of adrenal steroidogenesis that leads to a decrease in the synthesis of cortisol and aldosterone. Both female and male children born with CAH are exposed to high concentrations of androgens in utero; while males do not typically show any outward physical signs of this exposure shortly after delivery.

Pediatric adrenocortical tumors, particularly in young children, are typically functional. The average time to diagnosis is 5 to 8 months from symptom onset. Symptoms include virilization due to excess adrenal androgens (pubic hair, acne, clitoromegaly/penile enlargement, voice changes, facial hair, and hypertension) [Michalkiewicz E et al., 2004]. Many tumors secrete multiple hormones. If a tumor is identified, staging will include cross-sectional imaging with CT, PET/CT, or MRI of the chest, abdomen, and pelvis, with visualization of lymph nodes.

Hamartoma of the hypothalamus represents a well-known but rare cause of central precocious puberty and gelastic seizures. Patients usually have an elevated gonadotropin and testosterone levels. Hypothalamic hamartomas function as an accessory hypothalamus [Hochman H.I. et al., 1981]. When the facilities for gamma knife resection of the tumor is available, it can be used for resection which usually has good outcomes which may be comparable with the conventional surgery. In our case, patient did not have any signs of epilepsy and mental retardation, so we limited with GnRH analog in the treatment.

Conclusion

Thorough history and physical examination are critical in diagnosing sexual precocity. In boys with PP, mandatory determination is recommended to study the level of 17-hydroxyprogesterone (17-HP) in the blood to exclude congenital adrenal hyperplasia (CAH), alpha-fetoprotein, beta-subunit of human chorionic gonadotropin (β -hCG) to exclude germinogenic tumors, to study the level of dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA) in the blood and/or dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate in the blood (DHEA-C) to exclude androgen-producing adrenal tumors. All boys with premature puberty and children with neurological symptoms such as headache, vision changes or seizures should be checked using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

REFERENCES

1. Berstein L, Gurney JG. Carcinomas and other malignant epithelial neoplasms. In: Ries LAG, Smith MA, Gurney JG, et al., editors. Cancer incidence and survival among children and adolescents: United States SEER Program 1975-1995. Bethesda, MD: National Cancer Institute; 1999. p. 139-148. Accessed 21 March 2020. <https://seer.cancer.gov/archive/publications/childhood/childhoodmonograph.pdf>.

2. Brito VN, Latronico AC, Arnhold IJ, Mendonça BB. Update on the etiology, diagnosis and therapeutic management of sexual precocity. *Arq Bras Endocrinol Metab* 2008; 52:18–31.
3. Desai M, Colaco MP, Choksi CS, Ambadkar MC, Vaz FE, Gupte C: Isosexual precocity: the clinical and etiologic profile. *Indian Pediatr* 1993; 30: 607–623.
4. Hochman H.I., Judge D.M. Reichlin S. precocious puberty and hypothalamic hamartoma. *Pediatrics*. 1981;67(2):236-244.
5. Kim, Y.J.; Kwon, A.; Jung, M.K.; Kim, K.E.; Suh, J.; Chae, H.W.; Kim, D.H.; Ha, S.; Seo, G.H.; Kim, H.S. Incidence and Prevalence of Central Precocious Puberty in Korea: An Epidemiologic Study Based on a National Database. *J. Pediatr*. 2019, 208, 221–228.
6. Krysiak Robert, Przegł Lek et al. Precocious puberty in boys. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinol and Metabol* 2014.
7. Michalkiewicz E, Sandrini R, Figueiredo B, et al. Clinical and outcome characteristics of children with adrenocortical tumors: A report from the International Pediatric Adrenocortical Tumor Registry. *J Clin Oncol* 2004;22:838-845.
8. Sørensen K, Mouritsen A, Aksglaede L, Hagen CP, Mogensen SS, Juul A. Recent secular trends in pubertal timing: implications for evaluation and diagnosis of precocious puberty. *Horm Res Paediatr*. 2012;77(3):137–45.
9. В.А.Петеркова, И.Л.Алимова, Е.Б.Башнина и др. Клинические рекомендации «Преждевременное половое развитие». *Проблемы эндокринологии* 2021;67(5):84-103.